

A HERMENEUTIC STUDY OF SUFI IMAGINARIES AND FEMINIST SPIRITUALITIES AMONG SUFI MATRONS IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

LATEEFAT ADEOLA IBIYEMI, Ph.D

Department of Arabic and Islamic Studies,

University of Ilesa, Osun State Nigeria,

ibiyemilateefat@gmail.com

PROFESSOR ADAM ADEBAYO SIRAJUDEEN

Department of Arabic Studies,

Federal University of Lafia, Nigeria

Abstract

The intertwining of Sufi imaginaries, the symbolic, mystical, and relational motifs within Sufi traditions and feminist spiritualities, offers a compelling lens. This study examines the interplay of gender, spirituality, and authority as exemplified in the socio-religious activities of *Sheikhat* (Sufi Matrons) in Osun State, Southwestern Nigeria. It explores how female Sufi practitioners and Secular and Islamic feminist thinkers engage Sufi stories, metaphors, and practices to challenge male-centered socio-religious systems. It equally attempts to construct more inclusive and embodied forms of spirituality. Using a qualitative approach informed by feminist hermeneutics and interpretive analysis, the study draws on classical Sufi texts alongside contemporary Sufi writings and how both resonate with the experiential activities of the Muslim Yorubaland Sufi Matrons. The study highlights how women and queer mystics have historically reshaped Sufi traditions, inhabiting metaphors of divine love and annihilation to claim spiritual authority and agency to their disciples. Findings demonstrate that Sufi thought mostly provides a symbolic and experiential language for articulating spiritual agency beyond rigid gender roles. Metaphors of longing, union, and ego-dissolution resist hierarchical theologies and open space for fluid, non-dual understandings of selfhood and divinity. Rather than resolving tensions between Sufi and feminist epistemologies, the research treats this phenomenon as fertile grounds for inquiry. It concludes that Sufi imaginaries, when read through a feminist lens, operate as vital spiritual technologies that cultivate vulnerability, ecstatic love, and embodied sacredness, offering radical re-imaginings of divine-human intimacy. The study further recommends interdisciplinary exploration and the inclusion of marginalized voices to expand the liberatory horizons of contemporary mystical practice.

Keywords: Embodied Sacredness, Feminist Spiritualities, Spiritual Agency, Sufi Imaginaries, *Sheikhat* (Sufi Matrons)

Introduction

In recent years, female Ṣūfī leadership has gained growing recognition in African Islamic scholarship. Within Nigeria, women who lead Ṣūfī circles known as *Sheikhat* or Sufi Matrons have emerged as influential figures that combine mystical devotion, education, healing, and social service. These matrons reflect a broader transformation of religious authority, where women increasingly negotiate spiritual space without necessarily confronting traditional hierarchies. Osun State is part of Yorubaland, a region with strong Sufi presence for example in the Orders like, *Tijaniyyah* and *Qadiriyyah*) with robust traditions of female spiritual figures. This study builds on that growing literature, centering *Sheikhat* in Osun State, using feminist hermeneutics and interpretive analysis to explore how Sufi imaginaries are mobilized to articulate agency and reshape gendered authority. They combine feminist hermeneutics with the actual lived practice of women in these spiritual spaces how they use metaphor, ritual, symbolic narrative, and relational authority to negotiate gender norms, claim spiritual agency, and reimagining hierarchy.

By focusing on imaginaries rather than simply institutional power, this study aims to explore more subtle dynamics, how symbolic/spiritual authority is claimed, embodied, contested, and transformed. Recent works demonstrate similar shifts like, (Reading the self through a hermeneutic of divine immanence: a case study of Shaykha Fariha al-Jerrahi) the work examines how a female Sufi leader resists patriarchal formulations by emphasizing embodied, relational, immanent understandings of self and divine presence. Likewise, (Sufi Feminism Women Leaders in African Sufi Movements by Hassan, 2023), it documents how women like Nana Asmau and Sharifa Alawiyya al-Mīrghanī have claimed senior spiritual authority in challenging contexts. This study builds on that growing literature, centering *Sheikhat* in Osun State, using feminist hermeneutics and interpretive analysis to explore how Sufi imaginaries are mobilized to articulate agency and reshape gendered authority.

Power and Authority in Islamic Traditions

In Islam, power and authority are both conceived as sacred trusts rooted in moral responsibility, justice and accountability before Allah. It requires ability and capability. It is neither hereditary nor monolithic. It is historically distributed among jurists, scholars, rulers, and spiritual guides. It is as a divined gift and as directed by Allah, He gives the power to whom He chooses. The Quran says:

قُلِ اللَّهُمَّ مَالِكَ الْمُلْكِ تُؤْتِي الْمُلْكَ مَنْ تَشَاءُ وَتَنْزِعُ الْمُلْكَ مِمَّنْ تَشَاءُ وَتُعِزُّ مَنْ تَشَاءُ
وَتُذِلُّ مَنْ تَشَاءُ بِيَدِكَ الْخَيْرُ إِنَّكَ عَلَىٰ كُلِّ شَيْءٍ قَدِيرٌ

“Say: O Allah, Owner of Sovereignty! You give dominion to whom You will and You take away dominion from whom You will. You honor whom you will and you humble whom you will. In Your hand is all good. Indeed, you have power over all things.” (Qur’an 3:26)

The above verse declares Allah’s absolute authority over all power, wealth, honor, and status. Leadership, kingship (mulk), and influence are divine trusts bestowed and withdrawn solely by Allah’s will. It reminds humans, especially rulers and scholars that earthly power is temporary, and true honor lies in submission to God. It thus implies that women and not men exclusively reserve the right to become leader as could be exemplified in the story of Queen of Sheba in both the Qur’an and the Bible. It equally explains how women and not only men have access to spiritual development and stages to be bestowed with spiritual and divine prowess as well as charisma.

This does not in any way contradict the Sufi reflection, as this verse (*Qur’an 3:26*) expresses *tawhīd al-af‘āl*, the oneness of divine action meaning everything that happens in the world (gain or loss, rise or fall) ultimately flows from the Divine Will. Sufis often recite this verse to remind themselves of humility, Contentment, Reliance on divine decree (tafwīd) complete trust in Allah’s management of affairs, where both have rights to divine spiritual growth and development.

Allah also says:

وَإِذِ ابْتَلَىٰ إِبْرَاهِيمَ رَبُّهُ بِكَلِمَاتٍ فَأَتَمَّهُنَّ قَالَ إِنِّي جَاعِلُكَ لِلنَّاسِ إِمَامًا قَالَ وَمِنْ ذُرِّيَّتِي
قَالَ لَا يَنَالُ عَهْدِي الظَّالِمِينَ

“And (remember) when Abraham was tried by his Lord with certain commands, which he fulfilled: He said, ‘Indeed, I will make you a leader for mankind.’ Abraham said, ‘And of my offspring?’ He (Allah) said, ‘My covenant does not include the wrongdoers.’” (2:124)

The above verse marks the divine elevation of Prophet Ibrahim (Abraham) to the status of a leader and exemplar for humanity after being tested by Allah and fulfilling all the divine trials, the verse refers to divine tests and commandments that Ibrahim successfully completed (such as willingness to sacrifice his son, establishing the Ka‘bah, and unwavering faith). Allah declares him as a model of

faith and guidance for all people. This means that, leadership and divine covenant are not granted to the unjust but requires righteousness and moral integrity.

Sufi interpretation of this verse also symbolizes the journey from servanthood (‘ubūdiyyah) to leadership (imāmah) through purification and obedience. It is only after spiritual trials does the servant become a mirror of divine guidance. According to their understanding of leadership, the verse teaches that true authority (wilāyah or imāmah) is divine trusts earned through inner transformation, not inherited or claimed by birth alone. The Sufi also follow the tradition saying often quoted in classical Islamic ethical or Sufi writings (Ernst, 2011):

كُنْ إِمَامًا إِنْ جَعَلُوكَ، وَإِلَّا فَكُنْ تَابِعًا حَسَنًا

“Be a good leader if you are made a leader; and if not, then be an excellent follower.”

From the understanding of the above quote, Sufi leaders draw legitimacy from their perceived nearness to God and their moral excellence. This opens a subtle but significant door for women’s participation, especially in spaces where the spiritual experience, rather than the legal text, defines authority. Thus, while formal mosque leadership remains male-dominated, spiritual influence rooted in charisma, teaching, and intercession allows women to play prominent roles in community life. It is apposite to mention here that the above cited tradition does not specify whether it is a man exclusively that can assume the position of leadership if he is invited and or made, hence a woman who possesses the qualities and requirements could also be made leader. This is the argument of the Islamic feminism in its contexts. It is understood that the same way a man can possess spiritual and social growth and development, so a woman can as well be bestowed with such a rare prowess.

Secular and Islamic Feminist Thinkers

Secular feminism however, often challenges patriarchal structures through the language of equality and rights. Secular feminist thinkers believe that men and women are equal in every human sense and should enjoy the same rights and opportunities. Their ideas are rooted in reason and justice, not religion. Writers like Mary Wollstonecraft (1792), argued that women are not inferior by nature but made so by lack of education. Also, John Stuart Mill and Harriet Taylor Mill (1829), added that a society cannot progress while half of its members are held back by gender restrictions. Modern feminists such as Betty Friedan, Gloria Steinem, and Bell (1963), hooks widened the discussion to include workplace rights, family roles, and the combined effects of gender, race, and class, they stand for freedom, education, and equal participation for women in every field of life without barriers or bias.

However, Islamic feminism, seeks to reinterpret Islamic texts and practices to affirm women's dignity from within the faith tradition. Islamic feminist thinkers such as; Amina Wadud, Asma Barlas, Sa'diyya Shaikh, Fatima Mernissi and Leila Ahmed among others have shown that the Qur'anic message and Sufi metaphysics both affirm spiritual equality. These scholars approach gender equality and women's rights through a hermeneutic reengagement with the Qur'an and early Islamic traditions. They challenge patriarchal interpretations that have historically limited women's roles. They argue that the Qur'an, when read contextually and ethically, upholds spiritual, moral, and social equality between men and women. They support their stand with verses such as;

“Indeed, the most noble of you in the sight of Allah is the most righteous of you” (Qur'an 49:13)

Also, in the Quran where Allah says:

“And their Lord responded to them: I do not waste the deeds of any doer among you, male or female; you are of one another” (Qur'an 3:195)

The above quoted verses are central to the claims of gender parity in divine worth and responsibility. They emphasize that the Qur'an's message is inherently egalitarian and that inequality arises from male-centered exegesis (*tafsīr*) rather than the text itself. More so, in Amina Wadud work, “Qur'an and Woman” she reinterprets gendered verses to highlight mutuality, justice, and reciprocity, (Wadud 1999), while in Asma Barlas' “Believing Women” in Islam underscores Tawhīd (Divine Unity) as a theological foundation for rejecting gender hierarchy. (Barlas, 2002)

Islamic thinkers therefore conclude for a gender inclusive *ijtihād* (independent reasoning) that reclaims women's agency within the moral and legal framework of Islam by revisiting classical interpretations through a contemporary ethical lens. Islamic feminists seek not to reject tradition but to restore the Qur'an's original justice-oriented ethos. Al Ilory in his ‘Falsafatul Nubuwwah wal anbiyaa fii dawhil Qur'an wal Sunnah (lit: ‘Philosophy of Prophethood and Prophets in the Light of Qur'an and Sunna), which has attracted global reactions especially on some precepts on women prophethood could be a good example of the gender inclusivity in the spiritual realm. This is by no means a sort of Islamic feminism in this direction.

Sa'diyya Shaikh uses Ibn 'Arabi's Sufi metaphysics to argue that divine love “*maḥabbah 'ilāhiyyah*” transcends gender boundaries, showing that both men and women can equally embody spiritual perfection in particular, uses Sufi teachings to argue that divine love transcends gender boundaries. Within this framework, female Sufi leadership can be seen not as an act of rebellion but as a recovery of Islam's

spiritual core where closeness to God, not biological difference, determines status and authority. Further explaining in the book, Shaikh interprets Ibn ‘Arabi’s teachings to show that divine love dissolves the rigid binaries of male and female, proposing an egalitarian Sufi anthropology where all human beings can reflect divine attributes regardless of gender.

Gender Classification, Spirituality and Authority among Ṣūfī Matrons

In Ṣūfī path, it is not only men that were addressed as subjects of piety, female are also embodied in the position of multiple dimensions of authority. According to Ibn ‘Arabi, Sufi women are included in the authority and the practice of Ṣūfīsm. He explicitly states that women can reach the highest stages of Ṣūfīsm. Ibn ‘Arabi thus believes in women’s abilities to achieve a strong piety and to become a gnostic and reach the highest stage of sainthood and mysticism. According to him, all the positions in Ṣūfīsm are equally accessible to women. Ibn ‘Arabi decried the erroneous position in Ṣūfīsm where gender equality is highly visible. He continuously includes women as part of religious courses and practices. In his opinion, there is no spiritual qualification conferred on men which is denied to women. (Ouguir, 2013). Ibn Taymiyah also described another Ṣūfī woman who is popularly known as Ummu Zaynab Fāṭimah bint ‘Abbās al-Baghdādiyyah has not only a spiritual leader of the ribāṭ al-Baghdādiyyah but also as a jurist and preacher. He explicitly approves of her performing sermons and of her religious leadership (Ouguir, 2013).

Schimmel (1922–2003), a scholar of Ṣūfīsm, in her book “The Feminine Element in Ṣūfīsm”, underlines the role of women in Ṣūfīsm. She points to the feminine aspect of mystical by documenting key elements of its history that concentrate on the phenomenon of the female, and not just the gender or sex orientation of woman. She lays the textual and historical groundwork for what has now become a wide topic of interest. Schimmel in her book, published in 1982, “The Feminine Element in Ṣūfīsm”, focuses on promoting the women Ṣūfī. She successfully relates the ideal practices and values of Islamic feminine mystical order which has since been taken up by scholars from various areas of disciplinary focus (Abrahamov, 2015). In another of her book published in (1999), *The Mystical Dimension of Islam*, she explains that Ṣūfīsm is practiced by men and women. Kugle (2007) in his work “*Ṣūfīs and Saints Bodies*” explicitly argues that many male Ṣūfīs do not take into account, neither on a principle nor on a practical level, because gender has stressed in the doctrine of *Fiqh*, since they consider women as not important.

Wadud (1999), in her book, “*Qur’an and Woman*” she explains reading the Sacred Text from a Woman’s Perspective, studies the Qur’an from a gender perspective. She explores the way woman’s position is explained in the Qur’an. She explains that the Qur’an does not promote oppression of women. She argues that God in the

creation of human kind does not distinguish between man and woman. The Qur'an presents both men and women as created from the same *nafs*. The Qur'an does not make any difference in this respect between men and women, only on the basis of praxis, which means faith and the practice of Qur'anic instructions.

The Qur'an is not patriarchal in character and does not approve the implementation of any patriarchal rule. Wadud (1999) also discusses some examples of women mentioned in the Qur'an, such as Maryam, who highlights Muslim women's active and exemplary role in Islamic society. She also explores the Qur'an's portrayal of man and woman with regard to the hereafter. The Qur'an addresses the position of the individual in the hereafter as a result of consequence of each person's work, not in terms of gender but in terms of the individual's actions and faith. The only distinction the Qur'an makes is on the basis of *taqwa* (piety) of the person. As Wadud (1999) argues, the Qur'an explicitly admonishes men and women to participate in the practice of religion. Allāh says:

مَنْ عَمِلَ صَالِحًا مِّنْ ذَكَرٍ أَوْ أُنْثَىٰ وَهُوَ مُؤْمِنٌ فَلَنُحْيِيَنَّهٗ حَيٰوةً طَيِّبَةً وَلَنَجْزِيَنَّهُمْ أَجْرَهُم بِأَحْسَنِ مَا كَانُوا يَعْمَلُونَ

Whoever does righteousness, be it male or female, is a believer, then indeed we will definitely recompense them their reward, according to the Fairest of whatever they were found doing (16:97)

Qur'an 33:35 corroborate the statement

إِنَّ الْمُسْلِمِينَ وَالْمُسْلِمَاتِ وَالْمُؤْمِنِينَ وَالْمُؤْمِنَاتِ وَالْقَنَاتِينَ وَالْقَنَاتِ وَالصَّادِقِينَ وَالصَّادِقَاتِ وَالصَّابِرِينَ وَالصَّابِرَاتِ وَالْخَاشِعِينَ وَالْخَاشِعَاتِ وَالْمُتَصَدِّقِينَ وَالْمُتَصَدِّقَاتِ وَالصَّامِتِينَ وَالصَّامِتَاتِ وَالْحَافِظِينَ وَالْحَافِظَاتِ وَالذَّاكِرِينَ اللَّهَ كَثِيرًا وَالذَّاكِرَاتِ أَعَدَّ اللَّهُ لَهُمْ مَغْفِرَةً وَأَجْرًا عَظِيمًا

Surely 'for' Muslim men and women, believing men and women,¹ devout men and women, truthful men and women, patient men and women, humble men and women, charitable men and women, fasting men and women, men and women who guard their chastity, and men and women who remember Allah often—for 'all of' them Allah has prepared forgiveness and a great reward.

From Wadud's interpretation, no restriction has been placed on women to acquire religious knowledge or perform religious roles. Thus, men's leadership and women's obedience are not Islamic but cultural constructs according to the thesis.

Muslim women's oppression and backwardness in any case and where it is found is considered to be due to patriarchal interpretations of the original sources of Islam, especially the Qur'an, in the centuries following the death of the Prophet. Women in Islam since then are discriminated against, and not considered as being on the same level as male believers. Islam since then, Wadud (1999) believes, is used as an instrument and weaponized to restrict woman's functions in society and to make her inferior to her male counterpart.

Al-Sulami (937–1021) says that there were notable women *Ṣūfīs* whose spiritual achievements were worthy of emulation by both men and women. Such exemplification of women in historical *Ṣūfism* is also indicative of a fundamental fact that Islamic faith and practice were anything but homogeneous. The Prophet said, "God does not regard your outward forms but intention". This is understood that the physical body of human being is nothing to God, be it colour or race, but the most important thing is the mind's intention behind a man's action. Also, the Prophet (S.A.W) said: "Mankind will be raised up according to their intentions (Al-Bukhārī, 1997; Al-Nawawī, 1999). That, according to the tradition indicates that everyone is going to be judged base on his intents behind every particular action.

Moreover, the most convincing of the arguments here is that according to *shari'ah*, it is proper to take socio-religious instruction from any woman that is knowledgeable, especially if one considers that two-thirds of man's religion can be derived from A'isha- the wife of the Prophet as contained in one popular tradition; "Get a considerable knowledge of your religion from this Humayra". The underlying factor here is the acquisition of knowledge and imparting it on others. The significance of education (especially Islamic education) is aptly captured in Sirajudeen, (2013). It is said that 'as a bedrock of human civilization, particular attention was paid to education' as Islam emphasizes its unique codes of life, culture, philosophy politico-economy and ideology discerning minds among Muslims. It noticed the sharp distinctions between the Arabo-Islamic civilization and Western civilization.

This aligns with Abrahamov submission that "When a woman becomes a saint "man" in the path of God, she is a man and she can no longer be considered a woman" (Abrahamov, 2015). These submissions therefore indicate that elimination of gender in the discussion of spiritual perfection is acceptable in Islam and that the ascension into mystical world is granted to both men and women among Muslims. Hence, attainment of gnostic knowledge as well as imaginaries and spiritualities are not exclusive properties of men but also women.

Sufi Tradition, Spiritual Authority and Sufi Matrons

Sufi culture and tradition is one of the most profound spiritual heritages in Islamic civilization today, rooted in the quest for divine proximity. Sufism transcends mere

ritualism and penetrates the interior dimensions of faith. It emphasizes *tazkiyah al-nafs* (purification of the soul), *ma'rifah* (gnosis), and *mahabbah* (divine love) as the cardinal means of realizing the unity of being *tawhīd*. Historically, Sufi orders have served as socio-religious institutions that mediate between the sacred and the secular, the divine and the human, through systems of initiation, spiritual discipline, and charismatic authority. Meanwhile, spiritual authority in Sufism is embodied in the figure of the *Shaykh* or Murshid who is their leaders. Authority is not conferred by lineage or social privilege alone but through spiritual attainment validated by a chain of transmission '*Silsilah*' that traces back to the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W). This chain legitimizes the spiritual charisma of the master and establishes the ethical framework of discipleship *murīdiyyah*.

However, the concept of authority in Sufism is not static. It evolves within diverse cultural settings. In West Africa, for instance, particularly among the Qādiriyyah and Tijāniyyah Sufi Orders, authority has expanded to accommodate local forms of spirituality and gendered expressions of religious agency. Thus, women traditionally regarded as disciples have gradually assumed more active and visible roles as Sufi matrons, spiritual healers, and mediators of divine grace. More so, In Yoruba Muslim communities of south western Nigeria, such women are often referred to as *Shaykha*, their influence extends beyond the ritual domain into moral formation, healing practices, and spiritual counseling. They embody what Fatima Mernissi (Mernissi, F. (1991) terms "gendered charisma", wherein feminine piety and mystical insight intersect to challenge patriarchal structures of religious authority. The authority of Sufi matrons is primarily charismatic rather than institutional. It flows from their perceived spiritual gifts, visionary experiences, and capacity to intercede for the community. Their gatherings often become spaces of healing, education, and empowerment, especially for women marginalized within formal religious hierarchies.

Sufi Imaginaries and Female Spiritualities in Osun State

Originally, Osun State is known for its strong spiritual traditions. Within this setting, *Sheikhat* act as cultural and religious intermediaries. They blend Sufi rituals with local modes of sacred expression songs, poetry, symbolic dress like wearing only white garments and call for public blessings. This fusion produces what may be regarded as Sufi imaginaries creative ways of experiencing the sacred that give spiritual meaning to everyday life. Imaginaries like metaphors and symbolic language drawn from classical Sufism and reinterpreted by *Sheykhat*. For example, the metaphor of the "Beloved" might be feminized or made intimate, or references to merging with the Divine might be appropriated to speak to women's experiences of marginalization, grief, motherhood, community care. Through them, women's spirituality becomes visible, authoritative, and socially relevant. Their healing

sessions, counseling, and teaching circles have become spaces where faith, gender, and communal wellbeing intersect.

However, the rise of untruthful Sufi matrons has introduced a culture of deceit where ordinary life challenges are reinterpreted as mystical revelations. It is observed that many of these women claim to possess special spiritual powers the ability to foresee destiny, interpret dreams, or reveal hidden secrets but often use such claims to exploit their followers emotionally or financially. Instead of guiding their followers toward spiritual growth, they have turned the sacred path into a means of manipulation through false claims, fake fortune telling, and misleading interpretations.

Proliferation of deceptive spiritual leadership: A Desiderata

Gender and Spiritual Power: It has been argued in some quarters (Ibiyemi, 2024) that recent decades have witnessed the emergence of apparently charismatic and learned Muslim women who are increasingly recognized as spiritual authorities. These women often referred to as *shaykhats* in Islamic parlance are taking on leadership roles. They are not only providing socio-religious instructions and spiritual mentorship but are also actively, responding to some unique psychosocial needs of women within their communities, especially in contexts marked by conflict and societal pressures. In male dominated societies where women have little access to formal religious leadership, some of these women resort to mystical claims as a way to gain recognition, authority, and financial support.

Contemporary global economic banality especially with the emergence of covid 19 and particularly in the African and the third world has wrought untold hardship on the lives of average man. This consequently led many of the people into various kinds of criminal activities in order to make ends meet. The emerging trends in the women spiritual leadership ever found amongst these people took advantage and launched this illicit and immoral commercialization of religious activities. Thus, commercializing spiritualism was resorted to by some of these pseudo-sheikhats ostensibly to extort money from unsuspecting citizens and disciples.

The turning of spiritual work into a source of income has consequently encouraged deceit. Many of these sufi matrons especially the scammers amongst them now use fortune-telling and spiritual cum clerical consultation as a means of livelihood instead of sincere acts of devotion and service to God. It is common among these people to exploit the socio-economic situation that has ravaged the society as well as the gullibility of majority of the populace who are looking for quick money to fall prey.

Public desire for quick socio-economic solutions has now become the common traits among the citizens many of who are women patronizing these scammers in

the name of spiritual engagements. Many people today seek instant quasi-spiritual answers to their problems such as protection from harm, success in marriage, or financial progress. This hunger for quick results has produced a vulnerable market for spiritual services where miracles are valued more than moral or spiritual growth.

Lack of proper regulation and supervision of socio-economic and religious activities of these women in spiritual leadership garb, it has given rise to social menace that has eaten deeply into the fabrics of both the women leaders and their clients. There are no clear structures to monitor or regulate the quasi-Sufi leaders, many of whom easily claim to be spiritual authorities without the proper training, lineage, or moral qualifications.

Embodied Sacredness and the Future of Gendered Sufism

The concept of embodied sacredness means how *Sufi* matrons express spirituality not only through words or ideas but through presence, gestures, compassion and service that recognize as powerful ways of connecting with the Divine. Their bodies, voices, and rituals are living symbols of divine grace. This embodiment reshapes Sufi traditions by making spirituality relational and communal. However, some of the Sufi matrons are untruthful to their followers they introduce a culture of deceit where ordinary life challenges are reinterpreted as mystical revelations under the name of showing special power to them. The future of embodied language is likely depending on how such forms of authority are recognized whether through institutional acceptance or continued grassroots work, *Sufi* matrons demonstrate that spiritual power in Islam can flourish outside patriarchal control.

It also bases on how they live and express holiness is reshaping Gender Sufism that creates a new understanding of spirituality where feminine wisdom, compassion, and care are recognized as powerful ways to connect with the Divine. This approach gives rise to a more inclusive and balanced form of Sufism, where both men and women share in the sacred, and where spiritual authority is based on experience, character, and service, not just gender or hierarchy. Embodying sacredness of Sufi matrons contributes to a neocolonial and gender sensitive Sufi discourse that transcends textual orthodoxy and privileges experiential knowledge. Their practices articulate an emergent Gender Sufism rooted in compassion, healing, and the metaphysics of love, where sacred femininity becomes a vehicle for rethinking authority and sanctity in contemporary Islamic spiritualities.

Conclusion

The study shows that Sufi matrons in Osun State are playing a vital role in shaping contemporary Sufi spirituality in Nigeria. Their practices and experiences reveal how women use Sufism to express deep faith, moral guidance, and social services, through their rituals and teachings, they reinterpret traditional Sufi values with

feminine insight and compassion. Their spirituality challenges male dominated religious spaces while remaining true to Islamic ethics. These matrons embody divine love and humility, showing that holiness transcends gender. Their healing work and mentoring strengthen community ties and moral discipline. They represent a living bridge between faith, culture, and gendered expression. Their example shows that feminist spirituality within Sufism promotes inclusivity.

However, some of these women also manipulate Sufi symbols and language for personal socio-economic gains or influence. Such misuse reflects a form of spiritual rebellion that undermines the ethical foundations of Sufism. Their actions blur the line between true mystical insight and self-serving performance. This duality shows that Sufi spirituality, like other religious expressions, can be both genuine and deceptive. Yet, despite these distortions, authentic Sufi matrons continue to uphold the path of divine love and humility. They reinterpret Sufism to empower women without rejecting its sacred principles. The study therefore calls for discernment between genuine piety and manipulative spirituality for the betterment of Sufism in Nigeria.

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